

Gravity Academy

&

Gravity Pedagogy

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Refugee & Immigrant (Problematic Mind Set Created by the Human Race)

The "Mind set Problematic" to legislate years of asylum without providing a worthy educational base for refugees and immigrants to enrich their intellect and empower their on decisions, including economic ones; however, modern slavery, disguised in shameful laws, is far from providing equality to a universal (Global) system under consideration my point of view:

Precisely speaking:

The problematic of Social Exclusion, under the political and socio-cultural paradigms involving the unconscious predatory chambered of societal and cultural attitudes.

Gravity Academy & Gravity Pedagogy de acordo com Salazar, (2013):
" {... } such an approach challenges surface-levels approaches to teaching about diversity and places the humanity of those who are marginalized at the heart of social justice." (Salazar, 2013, pp.121)

Bibliography:

Del Carmen Salazar, M. (2013). A Humanizing Pedagogy: Reinventing the Principles and Practice of Education as a Journey Toward Liberation. *Review of Research in Education*, 37, p.121. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24641959>